

Myopic households on a stable path: the neoclassical growth model with rule-based expectations

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Abstract

This paper extends the neoclassical growth model by introducing myopic expectations, where rational agents can only predict short-term economic outcomes and extrapolate them into the future using rule-based cognitive schemes. These schemes, grounded in behavioral biases such as myopia, anchoring, and overconfidence, replace the traditional assumption of model-consistent expectations. Agents' reliance on limited forecasting horizons results in systematic deviations from the optimal predictions of standard models. A key contribution of this work is the explicit derivation of analytical solutions under isoelastic utility and Cobb-Douglas technology, which allows for rigorous comparison with the Ramsey and Solow models. The model exhibits global stability, avoiding the saddle-path dynamics of the Ramsey model, and reveals equilibria characterized by excess savings, dynamic inefficiencies, and low or even negative interest rates –aligning with empirical observations in advanced economies. The model provides insights into empirical phenomena such as slow convergence, excess savings and over-accumulation of capital, while offering policy implications. It cautions against fiscal and monetary approaches that disregard cognitive distortions and advocates for structural measures, such as taxing savings or redistributing income, to mitigate inefficiencies and improve welfare. Its analytical tractability also supports extensions to broader frameworks, including DSGE and HANK models, enhancing its applicability.

Keywords: Expectations, Neoclassical growth, Bounded rationality, Projection bias, Myopic behavior, Dynamic optimization, Time inconsistency.

JEL Codes: C61, D83, D84, E21, E25, E71

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Introduction

The perfect foresight assumption of the neoclassical growth model (Ramsey, 1928, Koopmans, 1960, Cass, 1966) serves as a natural benchmark for evaluating alternative hypotheses regarding expectation formation. While this assumption provides a robust framework for analyzing intertemporal decisions, it may overlook the cognitive and informational limitations individuals face in practice. In this paper, we explore the implications of an individual’s constrained ability to foresee future economic outcomes, even when motivated by rational intent to optimize intertemporal utility over an infinite horizon. These constraints may lead to inconsistent expectations, as beliefs cannot fully incorporate the true underlying model.

We propose the concept of myopic expectations, where the individual can anticipate the short-term effects of changes in the saving rate but is unable to make accurate long-term predictions¹. In this context, individuals rely on the limited information available by making use, or projecting, their short-term predictions also in the long-term. For example, they might assume that the short-term income growth following higher savings will persist indefinitely. This behavior aligns with the concept of “projection bias,” as discussed by DellaVigna, 2009, which describes the systematic tendency of individuals to expect their future circumstances to mirror their present ones.

To formalize how to leverage on short-term information, we introduce the notion of rule-based expectations. These are simplified mechanisms through which individuals extrapolate current information into the future. For example, assuming today’s income growth rate will persist indefinitely reflects a specific rule-based expectation. Alternatively, an agent may believe that short-term growth will quickly dissipate and converge to zero. This framework is flexible enough to accommodate features from behavioral experiments or empirical evidence, offering a broad class of expectations that can deviate from rationality.

Within this framework, even the perfect foresight hypothesis can be viewed as a specific form of rule-based expectation, reflecting an individual’s capacity to utilize all the information provided by the model –including the computation of future interest rates– to form model-consistent expectations. In all other cases, individuals may make incorrect predictions, which can be revised over time as they incorporate updated information about changes in the state of the world.

The process of expectation formation, where individuals rely on their current state (and different starting points lead to different expectations), has been coined “anchoring”² by Tversky and Kahneman, 1974, and usually results in forecast errors, as shown by Campbell and Sharpe, 2009 among others. Particularly relevant in this study will be the effect of the combination of the cognitive biases of anchoring and overconfidence, which will lead to the formation of incorrect expectations and behaviors with potentially harmful effects on economic welfare. Reference can be made to Lovallo and Kahneman, 2003 and Malmendier and Tate, 2005 for a discussion on overconfidence, which provides an interpretive framework for our results.

Deviations from expected utility theory and perfect foresight have been widely incorporated into the neoclassical growth models to offer a more comprehensive

¹At time τ , the household can predict only the short-term evolution of the capital stock as a function of the saving rate, $k_{\tau+1}(s_\tau)$ (discrete time) or $\dot{k}(s(\tau))$ (continuous time), without knowledge of subsequent periods.

²For a complete survey on anchoring, see Furnham and Boo, 2011. The behavior of the individual in the current work is consistent with other observed cognitive anomalies, such as the “Reference point” effect and the “Status Quo/Endowment” effect. More details on these anomalies can be found in McFadden, 1999.

explanation of observed consumption behavior. For example, Foellmi et al., 2011 employs prospect theory to introduce reference-based behavior (expectations) in the Ramsey model. This involves evaluating choices in relation to a certain reference point – the status quo – rather than in absolute terms.

The combination of myopia with rule-based expectations configures a dynamic sequence of static optimization problems that leads to a complete dynamic solution. Because the agent assumes that its current decision will last indefinitely, there is no need to estimate the feedback from the expected interest rate (which depends on future capital intensity) to consumption. Therefore, the myopic problem-solving approach disregards the standard nexus that operates in the pure neoclassical growth model, leading to a breakdown of the inter-temporal relationship between consumption and capital intensity.

This paper is linked to several strands of literature, which will be discussed further, including Day’s work on adaptive economizing agents (Day, 2000, Day, 1992), Barro’s work on dynamic discount factor and time inconsistencies (Barro, 1999), and Evans and Honkapoya’s work on learning and expectations (Evans and Honkapohja, 2001). Recently, Acemoglu and Jensen, 2023 developed a theoretical framework to analyze long-run responses to environmental changes under general behavioral preferences, thereby extending and unifying several of the previously mentioned approaches.

An important attempt to constrain the neoclassical growth model on a contingent plan (status quo) is the stream of literature dealing with the adaptive economizing agent (Day, 2000, Dawid, 2005). Agents use (linear) approximated representation of the production function and an adaptive expected interest rate. They are willing to leave to future generations (terminal condition) a constant level of capital.³ All this provides a simplified future stream of expected utility value which leads to a static policy function for consumption, depending only on the current level of capital. Day’s work demonstrates global stability and for some low impatience rates, limit cycles and chaos. Similarly to Day’s economizing agents, the optimal solution in our model depends on a static policy function, which is determined by how the agent projects its current information into the future, that is, by its rule-based expectations.

It’s worth noting that, in our model, the evolving bias in expectations modifies the relative time preferences of the household, giving rise to a dynamic form of “effective impatience”, resulting from the interplay of expectation errors and a fixed discount factor. This connects our work with the existing literature that addresses the issue of time inconsistency in optimal planning. Strotz, 1955 showed that, except in the case of exponential functions, varying time preferences lead to inconsistent plans that should be addressed with specific strategies. When agents apply time-varying discount factors, they can delay saving and increase current consumption, which may lead to sub-optimal outcomes without institutional settings that force agents to correct such behavior (via pre-commitment, for example). Pollak, 1968 and Goldman, 1980 demonstrated the condition for the existence of a consistent plan (equilibrium) under time-varying discount factors. Barro, 1999 extended the Ramsey model along these lines and found that the interplay between interest rates and variable rates of time preference generates dynamic effects similar to those resulting from differences in the rate of time preference in the standard model. However, in this literature, myopia stems from changes in individual preferences over time rather than from limited capabilities in the expectation formation process. In our work, instead, the sequential optimiz-

³Another example of bounded rationality is found in Bellino, 2013, where it is assumed that agents project a constant income on the long-term horizon. Consumers set their consumption level sequentially, starting from the first period. This kind of adjustment process ensures stability.

ing process creates time inconsistency, due to the interaction between rule-based expectations and impatience. Biased forecasts lead to time-varying utility plans, even when assuming constant time preferences, as they alter the perception of discounted future income.

Barro’s no-commitment setup leads to sub-optimal postponed saving, higher interest rate, lower capital accumulation and lower consumption and welfare levels, for every impatience level compared to the pure Ramsey case. In our work, expected constant growth leads to higher savings compared to Ramsey, due to a systematic overestimation of the effects of savings on future income, which translates into greater “effective” patience. The excess of savings becomes critical for very low values of impatience, leading rational and uninformed households to a dynamically inefficient region, resulting in a reduction in consumption and welfare. We identify an impatience threshold corresponding to higher capital accumulation compared to the Solow golden rule. This threshold generally falls within a range of realistic values for the interest rate, meaning that, in a world where agents are not able to perform accurate forecasting, sub-optimal long-run capital accumulation is a likely outcome and even a small time preference shock could lead to a significant reduction in welfare.

Our approach is also related to the extensive research on learning and expectations, expertly reviewed by Evans and Honkapohja, 2001. In the case of the Ramsey model, they demonstrate that the perfect-foresight saddle path is locally learnable, and agents can converge to the rational expectations equilibrium by employing adaptive rules. A misspecified rational expectation equilibrium can arise from an incomplete representation of the saddle path. In such a scenario, agents can only partially learn the intertemporal equilibrium. For example, Eusepi and Preston, 2011 enhanced the Real Business Cycle (RBC) model by introducing a learning process into the expectation formation mechanism. In this approach, beliefs substitute the precise relationship between exogenous variables, the aggregate economy, and market-clearing prices, leading to systematic forecast errors but to a better empirical fit with respect to the original Kydland and Prescott, 1982 model.

Our contribution is similar in spirit, as myopic expectations distort the relationship between expected interest rate (future capital productivity) and the saving decision, despite the agents exhibiting forward-looking behavior. However, our approach is more parsimonious because it does not need to assume either the learning process of an equilibrium relation, or its mis-specification, as the analytical treatment allows for a direct comparison with the basic neoclassical model. Therefore, myopic agents with rule-based expectations tend to converge to an equilibrium different from the Rational Expectation Equilibrium (REE), even when making decisions based on an optimization process. Our behavioural assumption, along with the rolling optimization procedure and the particular rule-based expectation, even in a forward-looking behaviour, leads to a sub-optimal condition (Euler-equation) that lacks the forward-looking element (expected marginal productivity of capital).

In the categorical and definitional framework of Acemoglu and Jensen, 2023, the proposed model is characterized by a belief formation process that disregards the long-run implications of the true model, together with “dogmatic misperceptions” that depend on the state observed by the individual and are therefore subject to continuous revision.

The main contribution of this work is to introduce myopia alongside rule-based expectations into the neoclassical analytical model and to study analytically its properties and implications in terms of dynamic stability, welfare, and factor allocation. The model is compared with the neoclassical Ramsey and the Solow

models in the case of golden rule savings, to highlight its characteristics more clearly. Compared to the Ramsey model, the main difference lies in the inability for agents to perform accurate long-horizon optimization and, therefore, to internalize the expected interest rates. This generally leads to a globally stable equilibrium rather than to saddle path (in)stability. Expectations of constant growth also lead to richer dynamics, including the possibility of accumulating too much capital, i.e., remaining in the region of dynamical inefficiency that is excluded in the Ramsey model. The excess savings, generated by the individual's bias on expectations, can lead to a reduction in the economy's welfare level. Therefore, compared to Ramsey, where agents' impatience always leads to a reduction in the saving rate, in the myopic case, there is also the reciprocal case where an excess of patience can lead the economy to excessive investment levels and a deterioration in welfare, compared to the optimum represented by Solow's golden rule. This results are consistent with empirical studies on overconfidence, such as Daniel and Hirshleifer, 2015; Lovallo and Kahneman, 2003; Malmendier and Tate, 2005. Moreover, as discussed in the final section, our findings suggest that, in a context of intertemporal optimization with overestimation of investment returns due to agents' myopia, an equilibrium characterized by consumption contraction and low (or even negative) interest rates is endogenously achieved, without resorting to external shocks.

The results can also be examined by considering the interplay between income allocation to factors and the expenditures associated with them. In the Ramsey model, high returns on capital always generate a capital income surplus that finances consumption spending, after the replacement of depreciated capital. On the other hand, the myopic model provides a broader perspective, as it can accommodate scenarios when a part of the labor income must be allocated, even in the steady state, to finance the depreciation costs of a large accumulated capital stock. Myopic households fear the effects of capital depreciation and are willing to allocate a share of labor income to sustain capital levels, even at the cost of negative interest rates.

The paper is organized as follows: section 1 presents the model in the case of exponential growth expectations, section 2 discusses its properties with respect to the Ramsey–Cass–Koopmans and Solow models, section 3 extends the model to include a different rule-based expectation mechanism and discusses the dynamic properties of the model. The last section concludes.

1 The model

We assume a representative household as in the standard neoclassical model. The expected utility at date τ can be defined as,

$$U(\tau) = \int_{\tau}^{\infty} e^{-\rho(t-\tau)} u[E_{\tau}\{c(t)\}] dt \quad (1)$$

where $u[\cdot]$ is utility with the usual properties, $\rho > 0$ is the constant rate of time preference, and $E_{\tau}\{c(t)\}$ indicates the forecast⁴ at date τ for the future value of consumption c at time t . Assuming perfect foresight, $E_{\tau}\{c(t)\}$ becomes simply $c(t)$, leading to the conventional Ramsey model. To concentrate on the mechanism of expectations, we will present the model initially without considering population and technological growth, which will be incorporated at a later stage.

⁴ $E_{\tau}\{x(t)\}$ represents the predicted value of the deterministic variable $x(t)$ that an individual does not know, due to either insufficient information or the inability to utilize the available information. This should not be confused with the role of expectations in stochastic models.

We call a household “myopic”, if it makes decisions at time τ , according to its current information set and forecasting capability, which is perfect only for a short time ahead. The household is still rational and willing to optimize its intertemporal utility on an infinite horizon, however, it needs to use some rule-based criteria to predict the future state of the economy. In particular, the household will make use of its “short time ahead” information in order to predict the value of future variables.

If we consider the saving rate as the decision variable, and income as the variable to predict, expected utility in τ should be maximized according to:

$$\max_{s(\tau)} \int_{\tau}^{\infty} e^{-\rho(t-\tau)} u[(1-s(\tau))E_{\tau}\{y(t)\}] dt \quad (2)$$

The problem for the household at time τ is to decide $s(\tau)$ in order to optimize $U(\tau)$, given the current expectations of future income $E_{\tau}\{y(t)\}$, with $t > \tau$, which depend on the instantaneous growth rate $\frac{\dot{y}(\tau)}{y(\tau)}$. At each subsequent date ($> \tau$), the household makes a new decision. In other words, the myopic household is not capable of dynamically choosing an infinite stream of future saving rates, but it myopically chooses a static one ($s(t) = s(\tau) \forall t > \tau$), which optimizes intertemporal utility, given its forecast of future income evolution. Then it repeats the process on each later date ($> \tau$).

A simple assumption on the myopic expectation formation process at date τ is that the household believes that income⁵ will grow in the future at the observed short-run rate $\dot{y}(\tau)/y(\tau)$, thus anchoring long-term growth expectations to short-term ones. Throughout the current section, we will adopt the idea that individuals tend to assume a constant growth rate for the future. In our case, this implies imposing that rule-based expectations align with constant growth expectations.

If we consider a Cobb Douglas production function $y(t) = k(t)^{\alpha}$, where $y(t)$ is output per worker and $k(t)$ is capital per worker, the expected future income becomes,

$$E_{\tau}\{y(t)\} = y(\tau) \cdot e^{\frac{\dot{y}(\tau)}{y(\tau)}(t-\tau)} = k(\tau)^{\alpha} \cdot e^{\alpha \frac{\dot{k}(\tau)}{k(\tau)}(t-\tau)} = E_{\tau}\{k(t)\}^{\alpha}, \quad (3)$$

which essentially means that the individual believes that short-term or instantaneous growth will also continue in the long term. If utility takes the iso-elastic form,

$$u(c) = \frac{c^{1-\theta} - 1}{1-\theta}, \quad (4)$$

substituting 3 into 2, the consumer problem takes the form,

$$\max_{s(\tau)} U(\tau) = \int_{\tau}^{\infty} e^{-\rho(t-\tau)} \frac{\left((1-s(\tau)) \cdot k(\tau)^{\alpha} \cdot e^{\alpha \frac{\dot{k}(\tau)}{k(\tau)}(t-\tau)} \right)^{1-\theta} - 1}{1-\theta} dt, \quad (5)$$

subject to:

$$\dot{k}(\tau) = s(\tau)k(\tau)^{\alpha} - \delta k(\tau). \quad (6)$$

Although the general solution is provided in the appendix A for the case of population growth, technological growth, and CRRA utility, we neglect for the moment exogenous growth trends and focus on the special case of logarithmic utility $u(c) = \log(c)$. The first step of the solution consists of finding the optimal saving rate as a function of current capital, $s(\tau) = s(k(\tau))$,

⁵If the household expects a constant growth of capital, rather than income, it can be shown that the steady state of the economy is not affected. Equations 9 and 10 still hold.

$$s(\tau) = 1 - \frac{\rho}{\alpha} k(\tau)^{1-\alpha}, \quad (7)$$

which, substituted into the law of motion of capital (6), allows us to derive the dynamics of capital in the myopic model,

$$\frac{\dot{k}(\tau)}{k(\tau)} = k(\tau)^{\alpha-1} - \frac{\rho + \alpha\delta}{\alpha}. \quad (8)$$

Equations 7 and 8 are obtained by Equations 26 and 27 in Appendix A in the special case of logarithmic utility ($\theta = 1$). The dynamic optimization problem becomes a static problem, where the household finds the best $s(\tau)$, which in turn determines the new capital endowment. Then, the household will make a new decision on savings, based on the new level of capital and new expectations of capital growth, which takes into account information acquired in the last step. The process continues until the steady state is reached:

$$k^* = \left(\frac{\alpha}{\rho + \alpha\delta} \right)^{\frac{1}{1-\alpha}} \quad (9)$$

$$s^* = \frac{\alpha\delta}{\rho + \alpha\delta} \quad (10)$$

1.1 Expectations and errors

The household makes a forecast error Ω when predicting future income. This error depends on the current date τ and the future date t that is being predicted, or in other words, it depends on the prediction horizon $h = t - \tau$.

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega(\tau, h, y) &= E_{\tau}\{y(\tau + h)\} - y(\tau + h) \\ &= y(\tau) \cdot e^{\frac{y(\tau)}{y(\tau)}h} - y(\tau + h) \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

This prediction error, at any given date τ , is positively related to the prediction horizon h , but decreases as the economy approaches the steady state. Equation 11 demonstrates that for a finite horizon, the prediction error is zero as τ tends to infinity, because $y(\tau)$ approaches zero and $y(\tau)$ tends to y^* (see figure 1 as an example). Additionally, as τ approaches infinity, the prediction error also converges to zero for an infinite horizon (see Appendix B.2 for the proof). This indicates that the household does not make any systematic error and correctly forecasts the future state of the economy as it approaches equilibrium.

The dynamic properties of the error are simulated and shown in figure 1 for the logarithmic utility case. Capital per worker converges to the steady state, after a shock of $\pm 40\%$ from the equilibrium capital stock. The figure includes dotted lines representing different forecast vintages, each starting on a different date and considering a forecast horizon of $h = 10$ periods. As previously mentioned, the perceived law of motion (based on exponential rules of expectation) and the actual law of motion interact. Even if agents anticipate a positive or negative exponential law of motion, the periodic revision of expectations leads to a stabilizing process.

Overall, the tension between rule-based expectations and bounded rationality, brought about by periodic re-optimization, constrains the parametric space available to achieve equilibrium determinacy. We demonstrate in Appendices A and A.1 that such a dynamic process has a parametric restriction for the stability condition that needs to be satisfied in the case of a CRRA utility function. The

Figure 1: Myopic model solution (black solid) for capital $k(\tau)$ vs 10 periods ahead rolling expectation (dotted) $E_{\tau,h}k(t)$. Negative shock from equilibrium capital stock (red, left). Positive shock (grey, center). Percentage error (right) (eq. (11)).

condition is derived for a model that exhibits exogenous technological growth rate x and population growth n :

$$\rho > n + (1 - \theta)[x + \tilde{\gamma}_y]. \quad (12)$$

It is useful to remind the reader that in the Ramsey model the transversality condition imposes a parameter restriction given by

$$\rho > n + (1 - \theta)x, \quad (13)$$

requiring the discount factor to play a significant counterbalancing role against the growth rates of capital and population.

The inequality of (12) resembles the one in Eq.(13), except that the myopic expectations bias $\tilde{\gamma}_y$ is added to x , where $\tilde{\gamma}_y$ represents the income growth rate estimated instantaneously by the individual at time τ (see Appendix A.1). What emerges from equation (12) is that the growth rate that actually influences the dynamics of the economic system, and that must be offset by the discount factor ρ , is not the exogenous growth rate x , but rather the one perceived by the individual, which incorporates an evaluation error. Similarly to the Ramsey model, there are different forces at play in (12): the constant rate of time preference ρ , the household's willingness to shift consumption between periods θ , the growth rate x , the population growth n and the myopic expectation bias $\tilde{\gamma}_y$. The bias leads, in general, to an overestimation of the effect of today's savings on future income variation. When the economy is undercapitalized ($k(\tau_0) < k^*$) the excess confidence in income growth, that is, $\tilde{\gamma}_y > 0$, determines additional savings. This can cause the optimization problem to diverge, if not balanced by a sufficiently high impatience

(large ρ) or a strong willingness to smooth consumption (θ close to 1). In the case of logarithmic utility ($\theta = 1$), convergence can be achieved with a positive discount rate ($\rho > 0$), as in the Ramsey model with no trend in technology or population. When the economy is overcapitalized, ($k(\tau_0) > k^*$), the fear of future income reduction, that is $\tilde{\gamma}_y \leq 0$, prevents the household to reduce savings by a sufficient amount.

The analogous problem in discrete time yields the same steady-state values of equations 9 and 10, provided that the standard discount rate transformation $\beta = 1/(1 + \rho)$ is applied, as demonstrated in Appendix C.

2 Comparison with Ramsey and Solow models

In this section, we compare the properties of the myopic model to those of the neoclassical models with non-optimizing and optimizing agents, namely the Solow-Swan at the golden rule (GR henceforth) saving rate and the Ramsey (R) models, respectively. As shown in the previous section, the myopic model differs from the Ramsey model because the household is unable to predict correctly the future evolution of the economy. As a result, it makes an error that gradually decreases when approaching the equilibrium. However, the accumulation of errors committed by the household affects the dynamics of the model and generates a steady-state that is different from the one of the Ramsey model. Table 1 displays the values of several key variables at steady-state for the different models under consideration.

Variable	Golden rule	Ramsey	Myopic
Interest rate r^*	0	ρ	$\rho - \delta(1 - \alpha)$
Capital stock k^*	$\left(\frac{\alpha}{\delta}\right)^{\frac{1}{1-\alpha}}$	$\left(\frac{\alpha}{\rho+\delta}\right)^{\frac{1}{1-\alpha}}$	$\left(\frac{\alpha}{\rho+\alpha\delta}\right)^{\frac{1}{1-\alpha}}$
Saving rate s^*	α	$\frac{\alpha\delta}{\rho+\delta}$	$\frac{\alpha\delta}{\rho+\alpha\delta}$

Table 1: Steady state values for Solow, Ramsey and Myopic models

2.1 Steady state

It may be useful to recall that sharing the same level of consumption across different generations, as happens in the Solow model within the golden rule, implies a zero interest rate. Moreover, at equilibrium, the capital steady state is the ratio between the investment share s and the dismissed capital rate δ , which at the GR level corresponds to α/δ , modified by the elasticity of substitution between labor and capital $1/(1 - \alpha)$.⁶ Introducing consumer optimization as in the Ramsey model means assuming inter-temporal selfishness. In this case utility is not discounted uniformly over time and generations, due to a positive impatience rate ρ . Such impatience implies to anticipate consumption and to introduce a positive interest rate at the equilibrium, $r^* = f'(k^*) - \delta = \rho$. This anticipation erodes optimal savings and therefore reduces the capital steady state level, as analytically ρ enters in the numerator and introduces a perpetual higher discounting

⁶It is useful to note that all models of Table 1 are special cases of birth and death processes, $\dot{x} = \phi x^z - \psi x^y$, where ϕ and ψ are the birth and death rates, and z and y are returns to scale parameters. The steady state is $x = (\phi/\psi)^{\frac{1}{y-z}}$.

$\alpha/(\rho + \delta)$. In the case of myopic behavior, the steady-state level takes the same form as the Ramsey model, except for a downward correction of capital depreciation by a factor of α . This correction arises from an overestimation of the impact of savings on capital accumulation, which can be interpreted as a reduced perception of capital depreciation. The internalization of the output elasticity of capital α in the myopic expectation process alters the neoclassical equilibrium. Different technology assumptions would lead to different deviations from the Ramsey model steady state.

$>$	k_{gr}^*	k_r^*	k_m^*
k_{gr}^*	-	$\rho > 0$	$\rho > \delta(1 - \alpha)$
k_r^*	$\rho < 0$	-	$\alpha > 1$
k_m^*	$\rho < \delta(1 - \alpha)$	$\alpha < 1$	-

Table 2: Ranking of capital steady state values as a function of parameters

Table 2 displays the relationship between the steady-state capital levels of the three models. For standard parametrization ($\rho > 0$, $\alpha < 1$), the Ramsey model always has a lower steady-state capital level compared to both the Solow model, i.e., $k_r^* < k_{gr}^*$, and the Myopic model, i.e., $k_r^* < k_m^*$. The first inequality depends on the household's impatience. The second, instead, depends on the bias in the expectations of the myopic agent, who tends to overestimate future income changes. When starting from a low capitalization, the household tends to overestimate the effect of savings on future capital growth, investing more than in the Ramsey case and accumulating more capital. In the case of excess capitalization, the myopic household still tends to overestimate the negative effect of a reduction in savings on future income and therefore chooses to maintain a higher saving rate ($s_r^* < s_m^*$), resulting again in a steady-state capital higher than in Ramsey. We will discuss the consumption level ranking in section 2.2.

Symmetrically, the equilibrium interest rate in the myopic case is lower than Ramsey ($r_r^* > r_m^*$), which is always positive in the presence of impatience. The inability to accurately predict the future leads households to make an error in calculating the expected interest rate. The process is similar to what has already been observed in the case of capital, and a graphical representation of the error, for horizon $h = 10$, is given in figure 2. Specifically, we define the expected future interest rate at time t , as perceived at time τ , as:

$$E_\tau\{r(t)\} = E_\tau\{f'(k(t)) - \delta\} \quad (14)$$

In the case of Cobb-Douglas technology, given the expectations about the future value of capital $E_\tau\{k(t)\}$ from equation 3, we obtain:

$$E_\tau\{r(t)\} = E_\tau\{\alpha k(t)^{\alpha-1}\} - \delta = \alpha k(\tau)^{\alpha-1} e^{\frac{k(\tau)}{k(\tau)}(t-\tau)(\alpha-1)} - \delta \quad (15)$$

We can therefore define the error made in predicting the interest rate with horizon h similarly to equation 11, as $\Omega(\tau, h, r) = E_\tau\{r(\tau+h)\} - r(\tau+h)$. Appendix B.3 demonstrates that the interest rate at the steady state is $r^* = \rho - \delta(1 - \alpha)$ and that $\lim_{\tau \rightarrow \infty} \Omega(\tau, h, r) = 0$. As observed for capital, the error $\Omega(\tau, h, r)$ tends to zero for sufficiently large times, indicating that the agent in the steady state is capable of accurately predicting future interest rates.

Replacement of the perfect-foresight assumption with exponential rule-based expectations generates a deviation of $\delta(1 - \alpha)$ from the Ramsey model in the equilibrium interest rate. This deviation, which we label as ‘‘myopic bias’’, is

Figure 2: Myopic model solution (black solid) for interest rate vs 10 periods ahead rolling expectation (dotted). Negative shock from equilibrium interest rate (red, left). Positive shock (grey, center). Percentage error (right).

due to the fact that the household cannot properly internalize the net benefit of holding a higher marginal unit of capital. We can define,

$$\rho_m = \rho - \delta(1 - \alpha) = r_m^* < r_r^* = \rho, \quad (16)$$

where ρ_m represents a sort of “equivalent impatience”, partly generated by the individual’s time preference and partly by their imperfect expectations. When the value of impatience equals the myopic bias, i.e. $\rho = \delta(1 - \alpha)$, two conditions are met: the steady state capital of the myopic model equals the golden rule capital ($k_m^* = k_{gr}^*$, see table 2), and the equilibrium interest rate r_m^* is zero. Otherwise, if $\rho > \delta(1 - \alpha)$, then $k_m^* < k_{gr}^*$ and $r_m^* > 0$; and if $\rho < \delta(1 - \alpha)$, then $k_m^* > k_{gr}^*$ and $r_m^* < 0$. The last condition states that when the household has a high level of patience, the steady-state capital accumulation is larger than the Golden rule level, and, therefore, the interest rate is negative. This specific scenario is depicted in Figure 3, which shows the standard textbook representation of the steady state for the three economic models considered.

It is well-known that in the Ramsey model, capital cannot be to the right of the golden rule capital because the solution would be dynamically inefficient. In other words, the individual could lower their savings rate to improve their utility in both the short and long run. However, the steady-state of the myopic model can remain in this situation of excess savings, as a decrease in the saving rate would lead to a significant decrease in future expected income and utility, according to the myopic household’s perspective. This would discourage such a reduction in savings.

Figure 3: Ramsey (grey), Solow (black) and Myopic (green) steady state capital. If $\rho \rightarrow \delta(1 - \alpha)$ the myopic investment $s_m f(k_m) \rightarrow s_{gr} f(k_{gr})$ and $k_m \rightarrow f(k_{gr})$. If $\rho \rightarrow 0$ then $s_r f(k_r) \rightarrow s_{gr} f(k_{gr})$ and $k_r \rightarrow f(k_{gr})$.

2.2 Welfare and policy

The focus of this section is to examine the discrepancy between the maximum steady-state consumption, which represents a benchmark achievable under the Solow golden rule saving level ($s = \alpha$), and consumption levels attained in the Ramsey (r), Barro (b)⁷ and Myopic (m) models. To quantify this difference, we calculate the percentage deviation of c_i from c_{gr} , where $i = \{m, r, b\}$. Figure 4 presents this deviation for various values of $\alpha = [0.2, 0.3, 0.4]$ and $\delta = 0.03$.

The use of rule-based expectations introduces time-inconsistent plans that result from the biased expected growth, which alters the perceived discounted stream of utility. At each time step, a new plan arises, leading to modifications in intertemporal consumption allocation. This leads to higher consumption than the Ramsey model when the time preference falls within the range of $\delta(1 - \alpha) < \rho < 1$. We emphasize that comparing welfare should be seen as an ex post evaluation of consumption levels between two distinct economies. It is evident that any path derived from myopic behavior and assessed within the discounted utility function of a standard Ramsey-type optimization plan would yield lower expected utility than the optimal solution advocated by pure neoclassical behavior.

It is worth noting from Fig. 4 that the impact of ρ on welfare in the Myopic model is non-monotonic. In particular, for $\rho < \delta(1 - \alpha)$, the myopic and patient household tends to save a consistent part of their income in anticipation of a very strong future growth that makes saving today convenient (as an extreme case, when $\rho \rightarrow 0$, $s_m \rightarrow 1$). This makes the maximum welfare level achieved by the Myopic model for $\rho = \delta(1 - \alpha)$ very fragile, as it is vulnerable to potential positive shifts in patience that can lead to a substantial drop in consumption. Noteworthy, this corresponds to a negative range for the interest rate, as shown in Eq. (16).

The model demonstrates that these types of expectations can lead, in specific critical cases characterized by an excess of patience (ρ), to economic equilibria (see Fig. 4, left panel) that are exposed to significant welfare losses in case of exogenous shocks. In such scenarios, policy measures aimed at stimulating consumption could prove beneficial in returning the economic system to a higher welfare, thereby escaping the trap of excessive saving. The same Figure 4 shows that this type of dynamics cannot be generated by models with perfect foresight,

⁷Barro, 1999

Figure 4: Percentage deviation from the steady state optimal consumption (golden rule case) for different values of $0 < \rho < 1$. Myopic vs. Ramsey vs. Barro, 1999 no commitment model.

such as the Ramsey model, as the decrease in ρ approaches the maximum welfare of the golden rule.

Figure 4 also presents the Barro, 1999 model, where the assumption is that individuals are highly impatient about consuming between today and tomorrow but are much more patient about choices advanced further in the future (Laibson, 1997), thus implying dynamic time preferences. Without any commitment technology, inconsistent consumption plans arise, and the individual tends to anticipate short-term consumption, ending up with less capital, higher interest rate, and a consumption level at the steady state that is lower than Ramsey, as evident from Fig. 4.

Unlike the Barro model, the time-inconsistent nature of the myopic model does not originate from a behavioral hypothesis translated into exogenous dynamic preferences. Instead, it directly arises from individuals' limited ability to form accurate expectations, which in fact dynamically modifies their intertemporal preference structure. Given the differences in the conceptual framework, the myopic model obtains results opposite to those of Barro's model. As discussed above, the accumulated capital is higher and the interest rates are lower with respect to the Ramsey benchmark, including the possibility of negative rates for low levels of impatience (ρ).

Myopic bias also affects the allocation of factor income expenditure. Two metrics, the relative excess of wage over consumption ($1 - c/w$) and the relative excess of capital income (π) over investments ($1 - i/\pi$), allow us to make some considerations about the allocation of income factors expenditures, despite the simplified structure of the representative agent economy. Using standard definitions,⁸ and expressing them as rates on total production we can write:

$$\begin{aligned} 1 - \frac{c(\tau)}{w(\tau)} &= \frac{s(\tau) - \alpha}{1 - \alpha} \\ 1 - \frac{i(\tau)}{\pi(\tau)} &= \frac{\alpha - s(\tau)}{\alpha} \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

The steady-state values for the indicators defined in (17) are reported in table

⁸ $w(\tau) = k(\tau)^\alpha - \alpha k(\tau)^{\alpha-1}k(\tau)$ and $\pi(\tau) = \alpha k(\tau)^{\alpha-1}k(\tau)$

Figure 5: Indexes of excess wage over consumption and excess capital income over investments vs. the logarithm of impatience.

3 for both the Myopic and the Ramsey models, and plotted in figure 5 across varying impatience rates ρ .⁹

	Myopic	Ramsey
$1 - \frac{c^*}{w^*}$	$-\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha} \frac{\rho_m}{\rho + \alpha\delta}$	$-\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha} \frac{\rho}{\rho + \delta}$
$1 - \frac{i^*}{\pi^*}$	$\frac{\rho_m}{\rho + \alpha\delta}$	$\frac{\rho}{\rho + \delta}$

Table 3: Allocation of factor income expenditure, steady states.

In the case of the golden rule, corresponding to maximum consumption, the flow of income that remunerates capital equals investments ($\pi_{gr} = i_{gr}$), and the flow that remunerates labor equals consumption ($w_{gr} = c_{gr}$). In the Ramsey model, $\pi_r > i_r$ and $w_r < c_r$, which means that part of the capital income is always used to purchase consumption. The equilibrium interest rate is sufficiently high to ensure a surplus to finance consumption after the replacement of depreciated capital. Table 3 for Ramsey shows that the capital income surplus increases with the net return on capital ($r^* = \rho$) and decreases with the cost of capital (δ), which determines steady-state investments. In other words, positive interest rates ensure that the excess of capital income is spent on consumption.

In Figure 5, we illustrate the allocation of factor income expenditure, corresponding to Table 3, as a function of the logarithm of the impatience rate (ρ). As impatience increases, the proportion of consumption purchased by capital income also rises. In this pursuit of immediate consumption, individuals sacrifice future growth by using capital income to buy more goods today. In the myopic case, as long as $\rho > \delta(1 - \alpha)$, there is an excess of capital income that is spent on consumption, similar to the Ramsey model. However, for lower values of impatience, part of the labor income is used in the steady state to finance the investment needed to counterbalance the depreciation of the large accumulated capital. Interestingly, in the case of myopic individuals, the economy reaches a stable equilibrium even at negative interest rates, provided that a portion of the

⁹ $\rho_m = \rho - \delta(1 - \alpha)$ is the “equivalent impatience”, defined in (16)

wages is used to purchase investments. The behavioral underpinning relies on the fact that the myopic household fears the effects of capital depreciation and is willing to contribute a share of labor income to maintain it, even at the cost of negative interest rates.

Figure 6: Ramsey vs Myopic transition from an initial condition on capital of 20% its steady-state value. The capital, consumption, production and investment ratio to their steady-state values is displayed on the left-hand panels. On the right-hand side panels are income percentage speed of convergence, saving rate, interest rate, and capital-to-output ratio ($\alpha = 0.3, \rho = 0.01, \delta = 0.03$).

2.3 Speed of Convergence

The equilibrium in equations 9-10 is a globally stable fixed point with speed of convergence λ_m , derived in appendix B.1,

$$\lambda_m = \frac{(\rho + \alpha\delta)(1 - \alpha)}{\alpha} > 0. \quad (18)$$

Fig. 6 shows the dynamic path to equilibrium of several variables of the model, after a shock that reduces capital to 20% of the steady-state value, as in Barro and Sala-i-Martin, 2003 with the goal of shedding light on the transitional properties given the same initial condition in relative terms. The myopic model shows a slower transition to equilibrium compared to Ramsey for the chosen set of parameters ($\alpha = 0.3, \rho = 0.01, \delta = 0.03$) as the distance of normalized capital, output, and consumption in the myopic case is larger than in Ramsey in the period considered ($\tau = [0, 40]$). Coherently, the income growth rate γ is lower than in Ramsey. On the other hand, the lower interest rate of the myopic model means that both capital and output are higher along the whole time path, as they are in the steady state. The figure confirms that the steady-state saving rate of the myopic model is higher, but it also shows a slower convergence speed. At time 0, the capital endowment in the Ramsey model is lower, which implies a higher remuneration of capital (interest rate r), which triggers a permanent higher saving rate. However, the gap in interest rates between Ramsey and Myopic decreases in time and myopic prediction bias becomes predominant with respect to the interest rate gap, determining a higher saving rate.

Figure 7: Parameters combination satisfying the condition $\lambda_m < \lambda_r$. For empirically relevant values of the pair (ρ, α) given $\delta = [.03, .06, .09, .12]$, the speed of convergence is lower in the myopic model compared to the pure neoclassical model.

The initial gap in interest rates reflects the degree of myopia. If the agent anticipated the same expected return on capital (with an interest rate of $r = 10\%$), they would adjust their consumption and saving rate more sharply, postponing consumption (e.g., by significantly reducing initial consumption, as in the Ramsey model). Instead, due to myopia, the agent perceives a lower interest rate because they project future capital growth exponentially, thus committing an increasingly large error over time.

As the agent is rational but myopic, the effectively lower perceived interest rate reduces the required adjustment in both consumption and the saving rate relative to its consistent steady-state level. This persistence in transitional behavior toward the steady state has implications for the empirical relevance of the neoclassical model. Specifically, it addresses the model's poor performance in capturing the transition dynamics of emerging economies, as highlighted in Barro and Sala-i-Martin, 2003.

We test the range of parameters for which the convergence of the myopic model (eq. 18) is slower than the neoclassical one¹⁰. In Fig. 7, we show the area of parameters (α, ρ) given an arbitrary $\delta = [.03, .06, .09, .12]$. The range of empirical and theoretically relevant parameters is matched as for the limited impatient ($\rho < 0.1$) and the observed capital share ($0.3 < \alpha < 0.7$), the model displays a slower convergence speed. Setting δ to higher values would shift the area to the right, increasing the impatience threshold to 0.5 when $\delta \rightarrow 1$ and narrowing the range of permissible capital share values.

3 Generalizing rule-based expectations

The entire approach described in the preceding sections depends on the assumption that has been made about the myopic nature of expectations by economic agents. As soon as one deviates from the idea that individuals have perfect

¹⁰The neoclassical model convergence is given by:

$$\lambda_r = \frac{1}{2} \left(\left[\rho^2 + 4(1-\alpha)(\rho + \delta) \left(\frac{\rho + \delta}{\alpha} - \delta \right) \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} - \rho \right)$$

with constant population and technology, as provided in Barro and Sala-i-Martin, 2003.

Figure 8: Stylized anchored expectations: exponential, constant ($\omega = 0$) and constant inertial ($\omega > 0$).

foresight, one falls into an inevitable variety of alternative assumptions. There is one way to be rational and thousands of ways not to be.

The hypothesis of the paper so far is that the myopic individual can calculate the short-term capital level for each possible saving rate choice and thus derive a short-term growth rate. The individual expected a constant growth rate for the future, anchored to the short-term rate, as in eq. 3. This assumption is essential because it leads to a constant overestimation of future output variations, which is one of the main determinants of all results obtained so far.

However, it is possible to assume that the myopic individual believes that the future level of capital is constant rather than growing, as in Dawid, 2005 and Day, 2000. This generally leads to an underestimation of future changes in capital and income, resulting in different outcomes compared to the previous case of expected constant growth rate. The analysis of this case will be conducted in discrete time, as it allows for a more intuitive representation of the mechanism through which individuals form expectations about the future and make decisions. On the other hand, as already shown in Appendix C, the results in discrete time are equivalent to those in continuous time.

As before, expectations are formed at each time τ , but the household believes that the future capital will remain constant at a given level, which depends on the law of motion for the next step ($\tau + 1$), plus an inertial component $\omega(k_{\tau+1} - k_{\tau})$ that adjusts the capital in the same direction as the first movement $\tau \rightarrow \tau + 1$. It is worth noting that the individual is still myopic, as they just consider the one-ahead time step to form expectations about all future values of capital. The inertial component, parameterized by ω , takes into account how much the individual believes that the observed short-term variation can influence long-term dynamics. If $\omega = 0$, the individual does not expect further variations in future capital, except for the one observed in the first period, and therefore the expected value of capital remains $k_{\tau+1}$. The old exponential rule, along with the constant rule with ($\omega > 0$) or without ($\omega = 0$) inertia, is intuitively presented in Fig. 8. The individual, at each time τ , perceives the level of capital at time $\tau + 1$ and derives the expected value from $\tau + 2$ onward by projecting short-term information. Hence, the equation for expected future capital is:

$$E_{\tau}\{k_{\tau+h}\} = k_{\tau+1} + \omega(k_{\tau+1} - k_{\tau}) \quad \forall h > 1 \quad (19)$$

Defining a logarithmic utility $U(\tau)$ and solving the optimization problem leads

Figure 9: Solow model and different calibrations for the ω -model. The ω -model exactly replicates the Solow model steady state for ω_{gr} . Parameters: $\beta = 0.97$, $\alpha = 0.3$, $\delta = 0.03$.

to a steady-state capital per worker level,

$$k^* = \left[\frac{\alpha\beta(1+\omega)}{1+\alpha\beta\delta(1+\omega)} \right]^{\frac{1}{1-\alpha}}. \quad (20)$$

The details of this derivation can be found in Appendix D.

Depending on the value of ω , the model can stabilize at different levels of capital. It is always possible to identify a value of $\omega = \omega_{gr}$ for which the steady-state capital is equal to that of the Solow Golden Rule ($k^* = k_{gr}^*$), or another value, ω_r , for which it is equal to that of Ramsey¹¹ ($k^* = k_r^*$), assuming the same parameters α , β , and δ .

In particular, if $\omega < \omega_r$, capital per worker accumulated in the economy is lower than Ramsey's; if $\omega \in (\omega_r, \omega_{gr})$ it is between Ramsey and Solow; and if $\omega > \omega_{gr}$ it will be higher than Solow. Figure 9 shows the trajectories for three values of ω , compared to the Solow model with golden rule saving rate. When ω is high, the household expects that the decision to save more determines a consistent capital accumulation in the future, which in turn will generate higher income. On the other hand, if ω is low, the household thinks that a high saving rate does not increment so much future capital and income, and therefore decides to save less, de facto not incrementing capital. It is worth noting that both high and low ω lead to a steady state consumption that is always less than the Solow correspondent.

In figures 9 and 10 we show the dynamics of the main variables of the model, after a shock that reduces capital to 20% of the steady state level, for different values of ω , namely $\omega = [10, \omega_r = 18.85, \omega_{gr} = 48.09, 75]$. It can be seen that for ω_{gr} and ω_r , the trajectories approach the same steady state as the Golden Rule and the Ramsey model, respectively. For higher values of ω , the individual tends to overestimate the effect of their saving choice, expecting a significant future increase in capital. Therefore, we observe in the figures high levels of both capital and saving rate in the steady state. In the limit case, by substituting $\omega \rightarrow \infty$ in (20) and then in (41), a steady state saving rate of one ($s^* \rightarrow 1$) is obtained, as

¹¹With logarithmic utility: $\omega_r = \frac{\beta(1-\delta(1-\alpha))}{1-\beta(1-\delta(1-\alpha))}$ and $\omega_{gr} = \frac{1-\beta\delta(1-\alpha)}{\beta\delta(1-\alpha)}$

Figure 10: Ramsey model and different calibrations for the ω -model. The ω -model exactly replicates the Ramsey model steady state for ω_r . Parameters: $\beta = 0.97$, $\alpha = 0.3$, $\delta = 0.03$.

individuals expect an infinite increase in capital.¹² It is worth noting that the maximum consumption is always achieved in the Solow model with the Golden Rule (Fig. 9). However, overestimating growth expectations can result in a higher steady-state consumption than in the Ramsey model (Fig. 10).

In Figure 9, it can be seen that the saving rate of the ω -model is lower than s_{gr} for $\tau = 0$. This means that the increment in capital is lower than in the Solow model. This observation can be demonstrated more rigorously by substituting the expression of ω_{gr} of footnote 12 into equation (41), describing the initial capital as a percentage θ of the steady-state capital, that is $k_0 = \theta k_{gr}^*$. With some algebraic steps, it can be shown that $\theta < 1 \implies s_0 < s_{gr} = \alpha$ and that $\theta > 1 \implies s_0 > s_{gr} = \alpha$. This reasoning can also be extended to subsequent time periods, i.e., $\tau > 0$, since $k_\tau < k_{gr}^*$ if $\theta < 1$ ($\theta = 0.2$ in the example of figure 9), meaning that capital grows monotonically. All this allows us to state that the convergence process towards the steady-state capital k_{gr}^* of the ω -model will be slower.

4 Discussion, policy implications and concluding remarks

The paper explored a neoclassical macroeconomic model in which individuals do not possess perfect foresight but form expectations with bounded rationality. In fact, individuals seek to maximize their utility but lack the capacity and information to accurately predict the future. These assumptions align with empirical evidence on expectation formation mechanisms reported in the literature, showing that individuals are influenced by well-known cognitive biases such as projection bias, anchoring, myopia, status quo effect, among others.

In the core part of the paper, we hypothesize that individuals expect a constant economic growth rate, anchored to short-term reference points. This hypothesis reflects the general idea, observed in both economic and public discourse, that the evolution of future income and production is perceived in terms of growth. Implicitly, this involves adopting an exponential expectation function. The combination of this hypothesis with the aforementioned cognitive biases leads to the

¹²In fact, the steady state capital is $(1/\delta)^{1/(1-\alpha)}$, which is the highest value achievable given the technology, regardless of β .

modeling of expectations presented in this study.

This formulation of individual expectations results in an excess of savings in the model, consistent with empirical evidence on over-investment, which has been attributed to biases such as anchoring and overconfidence (Daniel and Hirshleifer, 2015; Lovallo and Kahneman, 2003; Malmendier and Tate, 2005).

The model predicts equilibrium states with high capital levels and moderate interest rates. Notably, these equilibria can even be situated in a region that, in the Ramsey model, could not be reached by a rational individual due to dynamic inefficiency. However, the myopic individual can persist in a dynamically inefficient equilibrium because they lack the short-term incentive to reduce savings. This behavior stems from their tendency to overestimate future losses in capital and income (or loss of investment opportunities) resulting from reducing their savings.

The myopic individual maximizes utility by accumulating capital in a regime of lower interest rates compared to the corresponding neoclassical model. However, this equilibrium is fragile as it is susceptible to shocks that could alter the individual's preferences. Specifically, a positive shock on individual's patience would destabilize the economic equilibrium, triggering significant declines in production and income within a region characterized by negative interest rates.

This property of the myopic model has interesting implications for economic policy, as it predicts the possibility that households without perfect foresight may rationally choose to save and invest too much, with negative consequences for economic welfare. The real-world counterpart of myopic expectations is explained by Lovallo and Kahneman, 2003, who show how a combination of cognitive biases (including anchoring) leads managers to make overly optimistic forecasts for major investments. They exaggerate the likely benefits and ignore potential pitfalls, ultimately leading their organizations into initiatives that fall well short of expectations. The phenomenon of overconfidence in investment returns is analyzed by many other authors, including Malmendier and Tate, 2005 and Daniel and Hirshleifer, 2015.

According to the neoclassical approach, without frictions, the long-term equilibrium real interest rate must necessarily equal the time-preference rate and, therefore, be positive. However, after the financial crisis of 2007, economies such as those of Europe, the USA, Japan, and Canada entered the territory of negative real rates, sparking a broad debate about the motivations behind this phenomenon.

If we consider these countries as examples of a more mature capital accumulation process—where such economies have reached a capital level closer to the steady state (or balanced growth path) compared to emerging countries—then the pure neoclassical model cannot reconcile the evidence of low real GDP growth rates and negative real interest rates without resorting to exogenous disturbance factors.

The reasons that could lead to low interest rates are multiple, and much work has been dedicated in recent years to identifying them. Among the reasons for low interest rate there is ageing and demographic change (Aksoy et al., 2019), or the demand for safe assets (Caballero et al., 2017), or indebted household demand (Mian et al., 2021). The interpretative framework proposed by Bernanke's "savings glut" speech (Bernanke, 2015) plays a special role in explaining the process known as secular stagnation (Summers, 2013), where the global savings glut is a predominant factor in explaining low interest rates (see also Draghi, 2016). The theory explains the decline in interest rates in advanced countries, especially in the U.S., as an excess of savings from emerging countries compared to investment levels that have progressively decreased over the years. However, Barsky and

Easton, 2021 show that while the saving glut hypothesis can explain the fall in real interest rates from 2002 to 2006, due to an excess of savings that fueled the housing bubble, it does not effectively explain the persistence of negative interest rates after the Great Recession.

Economic policies implemented after the recession, aimed at lowering real interest rates to expand investments, continued the expansive trend of capital accumulation, though the effect on the real and domestic components is widely debated and seems limited as the QE liquidity flowed towards financial investments in emerging countries. Moreover, even in the post-COVID era, the return to positive real rates is commonly considered transitory (Holston et al., 2023).

Our model explains low interest rates of mature economies in a very simple way. Myopic expectations, applied tout court to the neoclassical model, align with the empirical evidence described above, leading to a long-term steady state with low or even negative interest rates without relying on international imbalance or other disturbance factors. Without abandoning assumptions of rationality, exponential discounting, and optimization, our description can explain the emergence of negative rates in the stabilization process of the economy by simply stating that individuals are myopic and forecast the future influenced by cognitive distortions such as anchoring, status-quo bias, and over-confidence. These biases, which reflect an overestimation of the effect of investments on future growth, are well-established in the behavioral economics literature, and ultimately shape an “effective” time preference, which deviates from the original, leading to different equilibria.

Furthermore, the model clearly shows that the level of welfare (measured as aggregate consumption) contracts rapidly when entering a negative interest rate territory. The only way the economy can sustain equilibrium is by allocating part of the labor income towards the purchase of capital goods. We believe this might manifest as undercompensation of labor in favor of investments, contributing to the widening gap between labor share and capital share observed over recent decades (Karabarbounis, 2024), potentially explaining the decline in the purchasing power of wages observed in many developed countries (Hubmer, 2023).

The myopic model with exponential expectations leads to distinct economic policy implications compared to standard models that assume only positive interest rates at equilibrium. If the myopic model is correct, policymakers – still reasoning within neoclassical frameworks – may misinterpret the economy’s state as a temporary deviation from medium-term equilibrium, even when the economy is actually in equilibrium. Hence, economic policies aimed at fostering the economy’s return to medium-term equilibrium may involve transitory measures instead of more structural ones. For instance, consider the scenario where the stationary state corresponds to a negative interest rate – a case widely discussed in this study. In response, the central bank might adopt a transitory monetary policy to smoothly guide the transition toward equilibrium. However, there is a risk that the chosen policy could prove ineffective as it targets a misleading equilibrium. This might mean missing the target by failing to account for global cognitive biases, leading to extra cost of misalignment and risking the loss of long-term credibility and the effectiveness of the inflation targeting tool. Our analysis also suggests fiscal policies aimed at mitigating the lack of demand due to excess saving, shifting the tax burden from consumption to savings. Examples include increasing capital gains taxes or reducing labor income taxation.

Moreover, for empirically relevant parameter values, the myopic model yields a lower initial speed of convergence compared to the Ramsey model. This result aligns with the existing literature, which suggests that the time required for emerging economies to converge with advanced ones is longer than what the pure

neoclassical model predicts. This issue, first identified by King and Rebelo, 1993, was later explored in greater detail by Barro and Sala-i-Martin, 2003. The model also predicts lower interest rates at the beginning of the convergence process, as well as lower consumption growth rates.

Finally, our framework has been applied to simpler neoclassical models, such as the Solow and Ramsey models, providing insights into their dynamics under myopic expectations and yielding exact analytical solutions. However, its potential extends far beyond these models. It can be adapted and integrated into a wide range of economic frameworks, including more complex models such as Dynamic Stochastic General Equilibrium (DSGE) models and Heterogeneous Agent New Keynesian (HANK) models, addressing the need to move beyond rational expectations, as recently advocated by Moll, 2024.

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Appendices

A First order conditions in continuous time

Following Barro and Sala-i-Martin, 2003, we consider a production function

$$Y(\tau) = F[K(\tau), L(\tau), T(\tau)] = K(\tau)^\alpha (L(\tau)T(\tau))^{1-\alpha},$$

with and $L(\tau) = L(\tau_0)e^{n\tau}$ and $T(\tau) = e^{x\tau}$. Defining capital and production per effective units of labor as $\hat{y}(\tau) = Y(\tau)/\hat{L}(\tau)$ and $\hat{k}(\tau) = K(\tau)/\hat{L}(\tau)$, where effective labor is $\hat{L}(\tau) = L(\tau)T(\tau)$, we can then write the per worker production as a function of the production per unit of effective labor, $y(\tau) = \hat{y}(\tau)e^{x\tau}$.

Households maximize at time τ the expected utility of per worker consumption, as in Eq. 3,

$$E_\tau(c(t)) = (1 - s(\tau))E_\tau(y(t)) = y(\tau) \cdot e^{\frac{\dot{y}(\tau)}{y(\tau)}(t-\tau)}.$$

Given that $y(\tau) = \hat{y}(\tau)e^{x\tau}$,

$$\dot{y}(\tau) = \frac{\partial y(\tau)}{\partial \tau} = \frac{\partial \hat{y}(\tau)}{\partial \tau} e^{x\tau} + \hat{y}(\tau)x e^{x\tau} = \hat{y}(\tau) \left(\frac{\dot{\hat{y}}(\tau)}{\hat{y}(\tau)} + x \right) = \hat{y}(\tau) \left(\alpha \frac{\dot{\hat{k}}(\tau)}{\hat{k}(\tau)} + x \right),$$

and one can write

$$E_\tau(c(t)) = (1 - s(\tau))\hat{k}(\tau)^\alpha e^{\alpha x\tau} e^{\left(x + \alpha \frac{\dot{\hat{k}}(\tau)}{\hat{k}(\tau)}\right)(t-\tau)}$$

Agents optimize over the time horizon $t - \tau$ with $t \rightarrow \infty$. Under the assumption of CRRA utility,

$$\max_{s(\tau)} U(\tau) = \int_\tau^\infty e^{-(\rho-n)(t-\tau)} \frac{\left[(1-s(\tau))\hat{k}(\tau)^\alpha e^{\alpha x\tau} e^{\left(x + \alpha \frac{\dot{\hat{k}}(\tau)}{\hat{k}(\tau)}\right)(t-\tau)} \right]^{1-\theta} - 1}{1-\theta} dt \quad (21)$$

where the last term is the result of the residual term (-1) of the CRRA utility integrated over the optimization horizon. We consider the capital per efficiency-units law of motion, $\dot{\hat{k}}(\tau) = s(\tau)\hat{k}(\tau)^\alpha - (\delta + n + x)\hat{k}(\tau)$.

$$U(\tau) = \frac{(1-s(\tau))^{1-\theta} (\hat{k}(\tau)^\alpha e^{\alpha x\tau})^{1-\theta}}{1-\theta} \int_\tau^\infty e^{\left[-(\rho-n)+(1-\theta)\left(x + \alpha \frac{\dot{\hat{k}}(\tau)}{\hat{k}(\tau)}\right)\right](t-\tau)} dt \quad (22)$$

We can derive the first-order condition for $\frac{\partial U(\tau)}{\partial s(\tau)} = 0$:

$$(\hat{k}(\tau)e^{x\tau})^{\alpha(1-\theta)} (1-s(\tau))^{-\theta} \int_\tau^\infty e^{\left[-(\rho-n)+(1-\theta)\left(x + \alpha \frac{\dot{\hat{k}}(\tau)}{\hat{k}(\tau)}\right)\right](t-\tau)} dt + \quad (23)$$

$$+ (\hat{k}(\tau)e^{x\tau})^{\alpha(1-\theta)} \alpha \hat{k}(\tau)^{\alpha-1} (1-s(\tau))^{1-\theta} \int_\tau^\infty e^{\left[-(\rho-n)+(1-\theta)\left(x + \alpha \frac{\dot{\hat{k}}(\tau)}{\hat{k}(\tau)}\right)\right](t-\tau)} (t-\tau) dt = 0, \quad (24)$$

The convergence of the integral is subordinated to the following transversality condition, that will be discussed below in appendix A.1:

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow +\infty} e^{[-(\rho-n)+(1-\theta)(x+\alpha\hat{\gamma}_k(\tau))](t-\tau)} = 0. \quad (25)$$

where $\hat{\gamma}_k(\tau) = \frac{\dot{\hat{k}}(\tau)}{\hat{k}(\tau)}$.

Given equation 25 and noticing that the two integrals appearing in the equation (24) converge respectively to

$$\frac{1}{\rho - n - (1 - \theta)(x + \alpha\hat{\gamma}_k(\tau))}$$

$$\frac{1}{(\rho - n - (1 - \theta)(x + \alpha\hat{\gamma}_k(\tau)))^2}$$

we can derive the optimal saving rate $s(\tau)$ as:

$$s(\tau) = 1 - \frac{\rho - n - (1 - \theta)(x + \alpha\hat{\gamma}_k(\tau))}{\alpha} \hat{k}(\tau)^{1-\alpha}, \quad (26)$$

Once substitute in the capital law of motion we get:

$$\frac{\dot{\hat{k}}(\tau)}{\hat{k}(\tau)} = \hat{k}(\tau)^{\alpha-1} - \frac{\rho + \alpha\delta - (1 - \alpha)n - (1 - \theta - \alpha)x - \alpha(1 - \theta)\hat{\gamma}_k(\tau)}{\alpha} \quad (27)$$

Which delivers the following steady state:

$$k^* = \left(\frac{\alpha}{\alpha(\delta + n + x) + \rho - n - (1 - \theta)x} \right)^{\frac{1}{1-\alpha}}$$

$$s^* = \frac{\alpha\delta}{\alpha(\delta + n + x) + \rho - n - (1 - \theta)x}.$$

In the case of log-utility without population and technological trend, we get the main text equation (9) and (10).

A.1 Integral convergence condition

The convergence condition for integral 22 is contingent upon satisfying equation 25. Since $t - \tau > 0$ for all t , the convergence condition of the integral depends on the following constraint:

$$\rho > n + (1 - \theta)(x + \alpha\hat{\gamma}_k(\tau)). \quad (28)$$

From Eq. (34) of Appendix B, we can compute the derivative of $\hat{\gamma}_k(\tau)$ over τ as:

$$\frac{\partial \hat{\gamma}_k(\tau)}{\partial \tau} = \tilde{k} \left[\frac{\lambda^2}{(\tilde{k} + e^{-\lambda\tau})^2} e^{-\lambda\tau} \right] \quad (29)$$

where $\tilde{k} = [k(\tau_0) - k^*]/k^*$. The result has an intuitive economic interpretation, stating that the expected growth rate bias on future capital $\hat{\gamma}_k(\tau)$ is positive only if $k(\tau_0) < k^*$ but decreases in time, until reaching zero at the steady state, see Eq. (35). On the other hand, if $k(\tau_0) > k^*$, $\hat{\gamma}_k(\tau)$ is always negative and increases in time towards zero. Therefore, it is possible to identify a value of $\hat{\gamma}_k(\tau)$ that is

a necessary and sufficient condition for equation (28) to be satisfied for every τ . This value, $\tilde{\gamma}_k$, can be expressed as:

$$\tilde{\gamma}_k = \begin{cases} \hat{\gamma}_k(\tau_0) > 0 & \text{if } k(\tau_0) < k^* \\ \hat{\gamma}_k(\infty) = 0 & \text{if } k(\tau_0) > k^* \end{cases} \quad (30)$$

Then Eq. (28) becomes $\rho > n + (1 - \theta)(x + \alpha\tilde{\gamma}_k)$, which can also be written in terms of income growth rate as,

$$\rho > n + (1 - \theta)(x + \tilde{\gamma}_y), \quad (31)$$

considering the straightforward relation between capital and income growth rates, $\hat{\gamma}_y(\tau) = \alpha\hat{\gamma}_k(\tau) \forall \tau$.

B Stability and errors

In this section we collect some results concerning convergence, stability and errors in the expectation formation process.

B.1 Convergence to the equilibrium

Under the convergence condition presented in appendix A.1, $\lim_{\tau \rightarrow \infty} k(\tau) = k^*$. Following Romer, 1996, the first order Taylor series approximation of $\dot{k}(\tau)$ around $k = k^*$ yields

$$\dot{k}(\tau) = \left. \frac{\partial \dot{k}(\tau)}{\partial k(\tau)} \right|_{k^*} [k(\tau) - k^*].$$

Differentiating equation (8) for $k(\tau)$ and using the expression of the steady state of capital in eq. 9, leads to:

$$\left. \frac{\partial \dot{k}(\tau)}{\partial k(\tau)} \right|_{k^*} = \frac{(\rho + \alpha\delta)(\alpha - 1)}{\alpha} < 0.$$

Therefore, the first-order Taylor expansion around the steady state is

$$k(t) = k^* + e^{-\lambda t} [k(\tau_0) - k^*], \quad (32)$$

with

$$\lambda = - \left. \frac{\partial \dot{k}(\tau)}{\partial k(\tau)} \right|_{k^*} = \frac{(\rho + \alpha\delta)(1 - \alpha)}{\alpha} > 0.$$

B.2 Error in future income expectations

To compute the asymptotic behavior of $\Omega(\tau, h, y)$ for both $\tau \rightarrow \infty$ and $h \rightarrow \infty$, without much loss of generality, we assume that the prediction horizon h is a multiple of τ : $h = m\tau$. This implies that $h \rightarrow \infty$ when $\tau \rightarrow \infty$, and we can write eq. 11 as

$$\lim_{\tau \rightarrow \infty} \Omega(\tau, h, y) = y(\tau) \cdot e^{\frac{y(\tau)}{y(\tau)} m\tau} - y((1 + m)\tau) = y^* \cdot \lim_{\tau \rightarrow \infty} \left[e^{\frac{y(\tau)}{y(\tau)} m\tau} - 1 \right]. \quad (33)$$

As $y(\tau) = k(\tau)^\alpha$, we can write the limit as

$$(k^*)^\alpha \cdot \lim_{\tau \rightarrow \infty} \left[e^{\alpha \frac{\dot{k}(\tau)}{k(\tau)} m \tau} - 1 \right].$$

Using equation (32), we derive

$$\frac{\dot{k}(\tau)}{k(\tau)} = -\frac{\lambda e^{-\lambda \tau} [k(\tau_0) - k^*]}{k^* + [k(\tau_0) - k^*] e^{-\lambda \tau}} = -\frac{\lambda e^{-\lambda \tau}}{\tilde{k} + e^{-\lambda \tau}}, \quad (34)$$

where $\tilde{k} = [k(\tau_0) - k^*]/k^*$. It follows that

$$\lim_{\tau \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\dot{k}(\tau)}{k(\tau)} m \tau = -\frac{\tau \lambda e^{-\lambda \tau}}{\tilde{k} + e^{-\lambda \tau}} m = 0. \quad (35)$$

Therefore, the prediction error Ω made by the myopic individual tends to zero:

$$\lim_{\tau \rightarrow \infty} \Omega(\tau, h, y) = 0$$

B.3 Interest rate bias

Differentiating saving rate, as in equation 7, with respect to time, we get:

$$\dot{s}(\tau) = (1 - \alpha) \frac{\rho}{\alpha} k(\tau)^{-\alpha} \cdot \dot{k}(\tau). \quad (36)$$

Combining equations 8 and (36), one obtains,

$$\dot{s}(\tau) = \frac{\rho(1 - \alpha)}{\alpha} \left(1 - \frac{\rho + \alpha \delta}{\alpha} k(\tau)^{1-\alpha} \right). \quad (37)$$

Considering that $r(\tau) = \alpha k(\tau)^{\alpha-1} - \delta$ and substituting $k(\tau)$ in (37), it becomes,

$$\dot{s}(\tau) = \frac{\rho(1 - \alpha)}{\alpha} k(\tau)^{1-\alpha} \left(\frac{r(\tau) + \delta - \rho + \alpha \delta}{\alpha} \right).$$

At equilibrium $\dot{s} = 0$ and $k(\tau) = k^*$, thus it is possible to derive the steady state interest rate as:

$$r^* = \rho - \delta(1 - \alpha). \quad (38)$$

The excess of capital productivity $r = \alpha k^{\alpha-1} - \delta$ with respect to the ‘equivalent impatience’ $\rho_m = \rho - \delta(1 - \alpha)$ leads to a decrease in the saving rate (see Section 2.1), diminishing capital accumulation. The saving rate stabilizes when the interest rate is equal to ρ_m .

In light of equation (15), the error $\Omega(\tau, h, r) = E_\tau\{r(\tau + h)\} - r(\tau + h)$, committed when predicting the future interest rate with horizon $h = t - \tau$, becomes:

$$\Omega(\tau, h, r) = \alpha k(\tau)^{\alpha-1} e^{\frac{\dot{k}(\tau)}{k(\tau)} h(\alpha-1)} - \delta - r(\tau + h). \quad (39)$$

Replicating the mathematical steps described in Appendix B.1 (from equation (33)), one can demonstrate that $\lim_{\tau \rightarrow \infty} \Omega(\tau, h, r) = 0$. In particular, using the results of Eq. (35) and substituting the steady state values from eqs. 9 and (38), one obtains:

$$\lim_{\tau \rightarrow \infty} \Omega(\tau, h, r) = \alpha \left(\frac{\alpha}{\rho + \alpha \delta} \right)^{-1} - (\rho + \alpha \delta) = 0. \quad (40)$$

C Discrete time myopic model

Utility maximization in discrete time can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned} \max_{s_\tau, k_{\tau+1}} &= E_\tau \sum_{t=\tau}^{\infty} \beta^{t-\tau} \ln \left\{ (1-s_\tau) \left[k_\tau \left(\frac{k_{\tau+1}}{k_\tau} \right)^{t-\tau} \right]^\alpha \right\} \\ & \text{s.t.} \\ & k_{\tau+1} = s_\tau k_\tau^\alpha + (1-\delta)k_\tau, \end{aligned}$$

where $k_{\tau+1}/k_\tau$ denotes the capital growth rate contingent upon the capital stock one period ahead, a variable influenced by the corresponding saving decision. We write the Lagrangian formulation:

$$\mathcal{L} = E_\tau \sum_{t=\tau}^{\infty} \beta^{t-\tau} \ln \left\{ (1-s_\tau) \left[k_\tau \left(\frac{k_{\tau+1}}{k_\tau} \right)^{t-\tau} \right]^\alpha \right\} + E_\tau \sum_{t=\tau}^{\infty} \beta^{t-\tau} \lambda_\tau (s_\tau k_\tau^\alpha + (1-\delta)k_\tau - k_{\tau+1})$$

Before deriving the first order conditions, we solve the setup for the infinite periods such as:¹³

$$\mathcal{L} = \frac{1}{1-\beta} \ln[(1-s_\tau)k_\tau^\alpha] + \alpha \ln \left[\frac{k_{\tau+1}}{k_\tau} \right] \frac{\beta}{(1-\beta)^2} + \frac{1}{1-\beta} \lambda_\tau (s_\tau k_\tau^\alpha + (1-\delta)k_\tau - k_{\tau+1})$$

The household takes their decisions at period τ , considering the whole time horizon and taking a new decision at time $\tau+1$.

The first order conditions are:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_\tau} &= 0 \Leftrightarrow \frac{1}{k_\tau^\alpha (1-s_\tau)(1-\beta)} = \lambda_\tau \\ \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial k_{\tau+1}} &= 0 \Leftrightarrow \frac{\alpha \beta}{k_{\tau+1}(1-\beta)^2} = \lambda_\tau \\ \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \lambda_\tau} &= 0 \Leftrightarrow k_\tau = s_\tau k_\tau^\alpha + (1-\delta)k_\tau \end{aligned}$$

It is worth noting that, in the second equation, the myopic behavior implies that the households do not internalize the expected effect of a marginal unit of capital in the next period $\alpha s_{\tau+1} k_{\tau+1}^{\alpha-1} - (1-\delta)$. Combining the F.o.c.s for optimal saving and capital we get the condition:

$$k_{\tau+1} = (1-s_\tau) \frac{\alpha \beta}{1-\beta} k_\tau^\alpha.$$

Substituting the law of motion of capital $k_{\tau+1} = s_\tau k_\tau^\alpha + (1-\delta)k_\tau$, after some manipulations, we obtain the optimal saving rate in period τ :

$$s_\tau = \frac{\alpha \beta - (1-\delta)(1-\beta)k_\tau^{1-\alpha}}{\alpha \beta + 1 - \beta}$$

¹³The following properties of infinite series has been used:

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \alpha^t x &= \frac{1}{1-\alpha} x, \\ \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \alpha^t t x &= \frac{1}{(1-\alpha)^2} x. \end{aligned}$$

Finally, substituting s_τ in $k_{\tau+1}$, we define the optimal law of motion of capital:

$$k_{\tau+1} = \frac{\alpha\beta}{\alpha\beta + 1 - \beta} \left(k_\tau^\alpha + (1 - \delta)k_\tau \right).$$

From this last equation it is possible to derive the steady state level of capital and saving rate, which correspond to eqs. 9 and 10.

D Constant capital expectations

The representative agent in time τ assumes that future capital will be constant at level $k_{\tau+h}$, which derives from applying the law of motion for one step, plus an inertial component $\omega(k_{\tau+1} - k_\tau)$ that adjusts the capital in the same direction of the first step. This inertial component represents all expected variations in capital beyond the initial period.

The agent's perceived law of motion can be described as:

$$E_\tau\{k_{\tau+h}\} = k_{\tau+1} + \omega(k_{\tau+1} - k_\tau) \quad \forall h \geq 1$$

If $\omega = 0$, the household expects capital to be constant at $k_{\tau+1}$. Given such relationship, the agent's discounted utility at time $t = \tau$ is:

$$U_\tau = \ln \left[(1 - s_\tau)k_\tau^\alpha \right] + \sum_{t=\tau+1}^{\infty} \beta^{t-\tau} \ln \left\{ (1 - s_\tau) [k_{\tau+1} + \omega(k_{\tau+1} - k_\tau)]^\alpha \right\} \\ + \lambda \left[k_{\tau+1} - (1 - \delta)k_\tau - s_\tau k_\tau^\alpha \right]$$

In order to find the optimal saving rate s_τ it is necessary to optimize the above function U_τ ,

$$\max U_\tau(s_\tau, k_{\tau+1})$$

subject to the constrain

$$g(k_\tau, s_\tau) = k_{\tau+1} - (1 - \delta)k_\tau - s_\tau k_\tau^\alpha$$

Then:

$$\mathcal{L} = U_\tau - \lambda g(k_\tau, s_\tau)$$

$$\frac{\partial U_\tau}{\partial s_\tau} = -\frac{1}{1 - s_\tau} + \frac{\beta}{1 - \beta} \left(-\frac{1}{1 - s_\tau} \right) - \lambda k_\tau^\alpha = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial U_\tau}{\partial k_{\tau+1}} = \alpha \frac{\beta}{1 - \beta} \frac{1 + \omega}{k_{\tau+1} + \omega(k_{\tau+1} - k_\tau)} - \lambda = 0.$$

Equating the λ s of the two F.O.Cs:

$$\frac{k_\tau^{-\alpha}}{(1 - s_\tau)(1 - \beta)} = \frac{\alpha\beta(1 + \omega)}{(1 - \beta) [k_{\tau+1} + \omega(k_{\tau+1} - k_\tau)]}$$

Substituting $k_{\tau+1}$ inside the equation with its law of motion:

$$k_\tau^{-\alpha} \left\{ \left[k_\tau(1 - \delta) + s_\tau k_\tau^\alpha \right] (1 + \omega) - \omega k_\tau \right\} = \alpha\beta(1 + \omega)(1 - s_\tau)$$

The optimal saving rate s_τ equals to:

$$s_\tau = \frac{\alpha\beta(1+\omega) - k_\tau^{1-\alpha}[(1-\delta)(1+\omega) - \omega]}{(1+\omega)(1+\alpha\beta)}, \quad (41)$$

and plugging s_τ into the law of motion of capital, one obtains:

$$k_{\tau+1} = \frac{\alpha\beta}{1+\alpha\beta} [k_\tau(1-\delta) + k_\tau^\alpha] + \frac{\omega}{(1+\omega)(1+\alpha\beta)} k_\tau.$$

The steady state can be computed by imposing $k_\tau = k_{\tau+1}$, as:

$$k^* = \left[\frac{\alpha\beta(1+\omega)}{1+\alpha\beta\delta(1+\omega)} \right]^{\frac{1}{1-\alpha}}$$

There exists a value of ω_r for which the steady-state capital is equal to that of the Ramsey model, which can be obtained from the following equation,

$$\frac{\alpha\beta}{1-\beta(1-\delta)} = \frac{\alpha\beta(1+\omega)}{1+\alpha\beta\delta(1+\omega)}$$

leading to:

$$\omega_r = \frac{\beta(1-\delta(1-\alpha))}{1-\beta(1-\delta(1-\alpha))} > 0.$$

The same comparison with the Solow-Swan's model yields to ω_{gr} ,

$$\omega_{gr} = \frac{1-\beta\delta(1-\alpha)}{\beta\delta(1-\alpha)} > 0.$$

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